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Critical Review of State of Health Determination Methods for an External Testing Application

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Summary

The scope of this paper is to evaluate an optimized State of Health (SoH) determination method for an external testing device for automotive service application. The increasing number of electric cars leads to an enhanced interest in the condition of the battery. Due to the batteries' large cost factor, a neutral evaluation of the battery condition should be sought. A deep literature research is performed to identify the currently discussed and used methods for SoH determination. In the next step, the methods are compared with each other with regard to the application in an external test device for automotive service application to identify the most suitable method.

KEY WORDS: After Sales, Battery SOH, Diagnosis, Testing Processes, Testing Device

1 Introduction

In recent years, battery-powered cars have experienced a significant increase in use [1]. The batteries in these vehicles age with time and mileage. As the lifetime of the vehicle increases, the condition of the battery becomes more and more important for the further use of the vehicle. Despite the decreasing price of Li-ion batteries, the battery remains as one of the main cost factors in modern Battery Electric Vehicles (BEV) [2]. For this reason, it is important to develop sustainable aftersales service strategies for HV battery diagnosis and repair [3]. In this field of interest, the condition of the battery is the most important information. One possible parameter to determine the condition of the battery is the State of Health (SoH). The SoH of BEV's is mostly described by the quotient of the nominal capacity which can be stored in the battery when new (Q_{new}) and the currently available capacity ($Q_{currently}$). This relationship is shown in equation 1.

$$SoH = \frac{Q_{currently}}{Q_{new}} \times 100 \% \quad (1)$$

A definition via the stored energy content is also possible. The SoH of Plug-in Hybrid Vehicles (PHEV) is mostly determined by resistance of the battery. An example of the relationship between resistance and battery capacity is shown in Figure 1. The two resistances shown in Figure 1a) and Figure 1b), respectively, are two characteristic points in a Nyquist plot of an impedance measurement. The results depicted in Figure 1 show

that although there is a correlation between internal resistance and stored capacitance, it is not accurate enough to determine the capacitance-related SoH directly from the measurement of the battery resistance.

Figure 1: Relationships between Capacity and Resistance [4]

Information about the actual SoH of the battery could also be useful for the after sales area, vehicle appraisers, leasing companies and second life users, to evaluate the residual value. Due to this fact, this topic has an importance that requires a more detailed investigation. With regard to the residual value of a vehicle, the remaining life of the battery will be a decisive factor in the future. For this reason, an independent, external testing device which can be used in workshops to evaluate the SoH seems to be worthwhile for future E-Mobility.

2 Methodology

This research is part of the master research project, in the curriculum of the Master's program Automotive Engineering and is conducted within the research program "E-Mobility Service" evaluating implications of the after sales service on the outlook of electric mobility. The research program is supported by e-mobil BW GmbH - funded by the state of Baden-Württemberg - and is conducted in the Center of Automotive Service Technology (CAST), Automotive Engineering Faculty of Esslingen University. Starting with the study "Electromobility – Implications for After Sales" [5] and [6] the topic "Maintenance and Repair Impacts on Electric Vehicles" has been presented at the EVS 31 [7].

To identify the most suitable SoH determination method for an external testing device, the following questions shall be answered during the research project:

- 1 What are the actual discussed and used methods for SoH determination?
- 2 Which boundary conditions must be fulfilled for the different methods?
- 3 Which parameters/data are required?
- 4 Which method provides the best results?
- 5 Are the methods suitable to the use in an automotive environment?
- 6 Which scale of testing is required?
- 7 Which data is available in an automotive application?

The research is split into three parts. The first step is a deep literature review and is performed to gain a basic knowledge of the topic and to identify the currently discussed and used methods for SoH determination. In addition, experts from science and industry are interviewed to enhance the depth beyond literature research.

In the second step the identified methods are divided into three groups, based on their functionality, and evaluated in terms of their use in an external testing device. In the last step, the methods are compared to find the most suitable one. The complete structure of the research can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Study Design

3 SoH determination methodology for an external testing device

Within the framework of basic research and literature research, the various methods for determining SoH were identified. These were divided into 3 groups: Experimental Methods, Degradation Methods and Adaptive Methods. In the following, on the one hand, the classification of the methods is presented, and, on the other hand, the most promising methods are briefly introduced below.

Experimental Methods: Direct measurement of battery parameters (e.g. cell impedance) and derivation of the SoH directly from these parameters.

Degradation Methods: Measurement of the relevant parameters and comparison with a model or a look-up table to determine the SoH.

Adaptive Methods: Measured values of the battery are transferred to a model of the battery implemented in a tester. This model then determines, depending on the parameters, the SoH.

Figure 3 shows the multitude of methods that were carried out through the literature review.

Figure 3: Overview SoH determination methodology

3.1 Experimental Methods

This group contains Methods which are commonly used for the investigation of cell and battery parameters. The experimental methods usually require a small amount of pre-test preparation steps in comparison to the other two groups.

3.1.1 Internal Resistance Measurement

With advancing age and use, the internal resistance of the battery increases significantly. Thus, it is obvious to determine the aging of the battery via the internal resistance. According to Ohm's law the internal resistance can be determined as it is shown in equation 2 below. [8]

$$R_i = \frac{\Delta U}{\Delta I} \quad (2)$$

To determine the internal DC resistance current pulses (ΔI) are applied to the cell. From the resulting voltage drop (ΔU) the internal resistance can then be determined according to equation 2. It should be noted that this value depends on pulse duration. To get comparable results a specific duration needs to be fixed, e.g. 1 second or 10 seconds. Since internal resistance depends on SoC and temperature additionally, both conditions also need to be fixed. As mentioned in Chapter 1, the measurement of the internal resistance is only partially suitable to determine the capacitance-related SoH.

3.1.2 Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) is a widely used approach for battery cell testing. Goal of this method is to evaluate the complex and frequency depending cell resistance (the impedance). Assuming that the impedance increases during cell ageing, EIS can be used to determine the SoH of the battery. For EIS a sinusoidal current of a small amplitude and varied frequency is applied to the battery and the voltage response is measured. The result is the complex cell impedance in dependence of frequency [8]. As well as the measurement of the DC resistance the impedance spectroscopy is only conditionally suitable to determine the capacitance-related SoH

3.1.3 Coulomb Counting

The method of Coulomb Counting is used very often to determine the SoH. During this procedure the cell is fully charged to 100 % State of Charge (SoC) and then discharged to 0 % SoC. Thereby the removed electrical charge is counted and compared with the maximum of electrical charge that can be removed from a new cell. The equation to determine the SoH is given in in equation (1), which was introduced earlier in Chapter 1. [9]

3.2 Degradation Methods

Since the Degradation Methods do not require complete charging or discharging cycles, the state of health can be determined much faster than with the purely experimental methods. This makes the degradation methods very attractive for use in an external tester in automotive service environment.

3.2.1 Gaussian Process Regression

Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) uses the voltage values in a certain period of time during the charging or discharging process to derive the cell capacity and thus the SoH. During this process the cell is charged or discharged under a constant current and temperature. To use the method, it is necessary to have a database of previously measured cells with varying SoHs. This database of curves with the corresponding capacity and thus the SoH are then stored in a lookup table. If a cell is now measured, its charge or discharge curve can be compared with the lookup table to determine the appropriate capacity or the matching SoH. The method is applicable for both charging and discharging curves. [10]

3.2.2 Differential Voltages Curves

The method of differential voltages (DVC) curves use the property of lithium-iron-phosphate cells that they form plateaus both in charge and discharge curves at low and constant C-rates. These plateaus form between 30 % and 60 % SoC, and between 80 % and 90 % SoC and have the property that they shift with increasing aging. So, the SoH can be derived from this shift. [11] In order to use this method, a lookup table or database is necessary, as with GPR.

3.2.3 Data Fitting

As already mentioned in 3.1.1 the measurement of the internal resistance potential provides information about the SoH of the battery. However, the application is made more difficult because the internal resistance is dependent on temperature and SoC. In the course of the Data fitting a characteristic data map or lookup-table is created to eliminate the influence of temperature and of the SOC. As well it is possible due to the data fitting to perform long-time predictions about the SoH and to reduce the time for computing. [8]

3.2.4 Big Data

The application of Big Data methods ranges from after-sales applications to research work on next generation products. Big Data is based on the evaluation of large amounts of data from which information can then be determined. By evaluating large amounts of battery specific data over lifetime, it is also possible to determine the SoH and perform lifetime predictions using Big Data methods. It may also be possible to predict, the key aging factors. [8]

3.2.5 Parity-Relation Method

With a parity relation method, the SoH can be determined while electrical engine cranking. The evaluation of the internal resistance of the battery is combined with the voltage drop when the engine is started to make the evaluation of the SoH more accurate and more robust against external influences. Evaluations of engine starting processes, which are presented in [12], show that information about the SoH of the battery can be obtained from the voltage drop during engine cranking.

3.3 Adaptive Methods

In adaptive methods, the measured values are transferred to a stored model from which the SoH is determined. The adaptive methods thus offer the potential to determine the SoH even faster than it is possible with the degradation methods. Prerequisite for this is sufficient computing power and a sufficiently accurate model of the battery.

3.3.1 Artificial Neuronal Network

Artificial Neuronal Networks (ANN) are the attempt to transfer the human brain into a technical application. A classical ANN consists of three levels of neurons that are coupled together via connections. The input level is used to read data from the system under investigation. The output level provides the results of the ANN. All levels in between are called the hidden level. The connections between the individual neurons have weighting factors that change the output of the preceding neuron accordingly and the result then serves as an input value for the following neuron. The neuron by itself has an implemented calculation scheme consisting out of an input function, an activation function and an output function. In battery testing, the ANN should simulate the function and the processes in the battery in order to determine its condition from the inputs. To map the investigated battery the weighting factors of the connections and the parameters of the neurons must be determined. To do so, the ANN must be trained with data of the battery under investigation. [8], [13]

3.3.2 Kalman Filter

The Kalman Filter is another method to determine the SoH of a battery. To determine the SoH, the filter estimates an output value from input signals and compares it with the measured values on the battery. The filter then changes its parameters until the difference between the estimated value and the measured value is minimal. For this it is necessary that the filter is fitted with a model that represents the battery as accurately as possible. Classic Kalman Filters are limited to linear problems. Since a battery is a non-linear system, there are extensions to the classical Kalman Filter, such as the *Extended Kalman Filter* or the *Unscented Kalman Filter*, which can be used to overcome this limitation. Another possibility is the linearization of the battery characteristics to apply a classical Kalman Filter, this way must handle the drawback of simplifying the correlations in the battery and with that an unclear statement of the SoH is the result. [8], [14], [15]

3.3.3 Fuzzy Logic

Fuzzy Logic is a method derived from pattern recognition for processing vague statements. Compared to classical logic with its fixed states 1 and 0, the values of Fuzzy Logic can also be between 1 and 0, depending on how the question under investigation fulfills the two boundary statements, represented by 1 and 0, respectively. When processing results with Fuzzy Logic, the logic checks to what extent the examined system fulfills the predefined properties. Based on these results, a statement about the system can then be made. In battery testing, the Fuzzy Logic is often linked with other measurement methods to obtain input values for the Fuzzy application. For the use of the Fuzzy Logic in the battery testing, as with the ANN, large amounts of test data must be available in order to optimally map the system to the battery. [8], [13], [16]

3.3.4 Observers

Observer or more precisely, Slide Mode Observer originates from control engineering and is used there to control many different types of systems. The system under investigation is described by an ideal function. The so-called switching function. In the ideal case the system follows this function. If there is a deviation from the mean ideal function, further functions are used to counteract this until the error between the ideal behavior and the system behavior is 0.

When applied to batteries, the battery is described by a collection of functions and parameters. The parameters must be determined in advance by measuring the desired battery and modeling it. When testing a battery, predefined output values are estimated from the input data and compared with the measured values of the battery. From the variables that have to be adjusted to minimize the error, it is then possible to deduce the aging condition of the battery. [17], [18], [19], [20]

3.3.5 Least Squares

The Least Square method tries to correlate the measured values with a minimum error. The Least Square method is connected to a model that represents the battery. The Least Square algorithm determines predefined parameters from measured data of the battery. The parameters are then transferred to the stored model of the battery, where the SoH of the battery is determined depending on the parameters. For an optimal determination of the SoH, the battery must be measured beforehand to adjust the model optimally. [21], [22], [23], [24]

4 Comparison of methods

Finally, the methods are compared and evaluated with regard to their application in an external test device for automotive service applications. To determine the evaluation criteria of the methods, the requirements for this use case are specified next.

An external SoH testing device for in-workshop usage should be able to evaluate the SoH of a given battery within an appropriate time frame. A time window between 30 minutes and one hour is considered to be appropriate for this purpose. The testing device must be able to communicate with given vehicle interfaces. To make the application usable in a workshop, weight and size limits must be observed. In order to guarantee a certain accuracy, the difference between the determined and the actual SoH should not be greater than 5 % in total.

In order to enable an evaluation of the methods, the parameters important for an external testing device for SoH-determination are analyzed. These parameters are: required data, advantages, drawbacks, robustness, accuracy, necessary interfaces, testing duration and development expenditure. In relation to these parameters, the individual groups show some advantages and disadvantages which are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Advantages & Disadvantages of SoH determination methods

Method	Advantages	Disadvantages
Experimental methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low pre-testing expenditure • High accuracy, when effect is measurable directly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Influence of cell chemistry • Influence of temperature
Degradation methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low required computing power • Simple battery models • Low influence of boundary conditions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • limitation to one cell chemistry • each cell type must be separately parameterized • High amount of measurements required
Adaptive methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quick to perform when computing power available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex modeling • High amount of required data • High computing power required

In order to be able to make a sound statement about the most fitting method for an external testing device, the methods must be validated for application in the envisaged environment. For this purpose, an evaluation matrix was created that contains the most important factors, which are extracted from the requirements introduced above. Following is a description of the different criteria that are shown in Table 2: Evaluation Matrix. *Test duration* evaluates the time consumption of the different methods. *Accuracy* rates the deviation of estimated SoH compared to the real SoH. *Effort in advance* rates the effort before the first test can be started, including battery model setup, training or parametrizing the model, while *Extensibility* evaluates the application of the method on more than one cell chemistry. *Boundary conditions / Robustness* assess the influence of ambient conditions in the working environment (e.g. workshop) on the SoH results of the different methods. *Availability of the required data* evaluates whether and at what expense the required battery data can be accessed. For the evaluation points from 0 to 10 are awarded and then multiplied with the weighting factors from Table 2.

Table 2: Evaluation Matrix

Criterion	Weighting factor
Test Duration	20%
Accuracy	20%
Effort in Advance / Extensibility	20%
Boundary conditions / Robustness	15%
Availability of the required data	25%

Figure 4 shows the exemplary evaluation using three methods, one from each group, respectively. The best method from each group is presented, since the entire matrix would go beyond the scope of this section. For the evaluation, an ideal value was assumed for each evaluation criterion; depending on the extent to which the methods in question achieved this value, corresponding scores were awarded. For example, in Coulomb Counting, the required information about the SoH can simply be read from the loaded or discharged charge quantity. For the evaluation, this is considered to be very easy to achieve, which is why 10 points were awarded here for the availability of the required data. The situation is different for the ANN's. Here the availability of data is very limited at the moment, which is why only three points were awarded here. The reason for this limitation is explained in the following paragraph. All other methods introduced in Chapter 3 were evaluated according to the same scheme as the three methods listed here.

For the SoH determination on the vehicle and the following evaluation of the different methods, however, it must be noted that the battery consists of a system of interconnected cells, power electronics and other components. Access to the required data is only possible via the BMS, to which, according to the current state of knowledge, only very limited external access is possible. Alternatively, the battery as a whole can be analyzed via the HV connections.

Experimental Methods	nr.	criteria	weighting factor	Coulomb Counting	
				points	value
	1	Test duration	20%	5	1
	2	Accuracy	20%	10	2
	3	Effort in advance / Extensibility	20%	7	1,4
	4	Boundary conditions / Robustness	15%	8	1,2
5	Availability of the required data	25%	10	2,5	
					8,1

Degradation Methods	nr.	criteria	weighting factor	Differential Voltages Curves	
				points	value
	1	Test duration	20%	7	1,4
	2	Accuracy	20%	7	1,4
	3	Effort in advance / Extensibility	20%	3	0,6
	4	Boundary conditions / Robustness	15%	8	1,2
5	Availability of the required data	25%	8	2	
					6,6

Adaptive Methods	nr.	criteria	weighting factor	Artificial Neuronal Network	
				points	value
	1	Test duration	20%	8	1,6
	2	Accuracy	20%	9	1,8
	3	Effort in advance / Extensibility	20%	2	0,4
	4	Boundary conditions / Robustness	15%	5	0,75
5	Availability of the required data	25%	3	0,75	
					5,3

Figure 4: Evaluation Matrix

The result of the evaluation of the methods presented above is illustrated in Figure 5. Different colors indicate the different groups. The Experimental Methods are marked light blue, Degradation Methods blue and the Adaptive Methods orange. According to the results, Coulomb Counting seems to be the most suitable method for determine the SoH in an external testing device for service applications. Coulomb Counting shows a high availability of the required data, due to the simple principle of counting the input charge, which could be counted directly and a high extensibility to other cell chemistries. Furthermore, Coulomb Counting is characterized by its good accuracy, the high level of robustness and the low effort in advance. Drawback is the extended testing duration, which is depending on the charge and discharge currents.

GPR and DVC are showing a high potential for a possible application in an external testing device. Both methods combine the possibility of reducing testing time compared to Coulomb Counting, a high accuracy, a high level of robustness and a good availability of the required data. Both methods are using charging curves and their time derivatives, respectively, so both data sets can be acquired similar to the Coulomb Counting. The main drawbacks for DVC and GPR are the large efforts in advance for fitting the look up tables with the needed data and the limited extensibility to other cell chemistries. Reason for the restriction of the extensibility is the fact that both methods are based on curve fitting algorithms. The charging curves of different chemistries vary.[8] [10] [25] [26]

As with GPR and DVC, it is necessary to evaluate large quantities of measurements in advance in order to use the further Degradation Methods. These are usually dependent on the cell chemistry, which means that each cell type must be parameterized separately. Another disadvantage of the Degradation Methods is the availability of the required data. As mentioned above, the data has to be collected via the BMS, which is currently only possible to a limited extent for third parties. However, very high accuracies and a fast determination of the SoH can be achieved in this way. Moreover, the other Degradation Methods also offer big advantages. Through Big Data applications for example, it can be possible to determine where to most aggressive loss of capacity comes from. [8]

All Adaptive Methods have in common that before the first test of a battery a lot of data about the specific battery must be collected in order to optimally adapt the models and equations stored in the individual methods to the cells. The adaptation in turn limits the extendibility to further cell chemistries.

For an example ANN's are characterized by their high possible accuracy and the short measuring time. Disadvantages of the ANN's are mainly their very long teach-in time, for which a large amount of battery data is required at the same time. Due to the large amount of data, the network can be adapted very precisely to the existing cell chemistry. This means, however, that the expandability to other cell chemistries is limited, since the selected parameters used by the ANN can behave differently with different cell chemistries as the

battery ages. The situation is similar with Kalman Filters. The accuracy that can be achieved with this method and the measuring time are very well compatible with the requirements. For example, in [27] a SoH measurement method using a Kalman Filter is presented, where the SoH of the battery can be determined within a 30-minute drive. The other methods described in Chapter 3 have similar advantages and disadvantages as outlined by the two examples. In general, it can be said that the great effort in advance and the limitation of the individual methods to a few batteries at the same time make the use in an external test device difficult. Before the tester could be used, a large amount of data must be collected in order to adjust the tester to one or a few cell chemistries. However, since the tester should be able to test as many different cell types as possible in order to ensure universal use in the service sector, these points make the Adaptive Methods impractical for the implementation in such a testing device at the present time. Additionally, the fact that the accessibility of battery information through the BMS is limited at the present time, most of the needed data cannot be achieved by the external testing device which prevents the use of Adaptive Methods according to the current state of knowledge. In the future this problem could be addressed by implementing norms and rules for a standardized access interface for such external testing devices.

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy is characterized by a low effort in advance and a good robustness. A drawback of the method is the dependence of the results on battery components like cables and connections. Furthermore, to reach good results a wide range of frequencies must be tested at different SoC levels, which results in a long test duration. The determination of the internal resistance with the Current Pulse Method, is characterized by a much shorter test duration, compared to the Impedance Spectroscopy. At the same time, the effort in advance is very low compared to the Adaptive Methods. Disadvantages are the poor accuracy and the accessibility of the data. For the evaluation of the accuracy and the accessibility of the data in Impedance Spectroscopy and the measurement of the internal resistance a further explanation is necessary. Since the present paper refers to an external measuring device, a measurement of the internal resistance or the impedance of the battery is only possible via the HV connector or separate leads. When measuring at the HV connector it must be taken into account that the applied current pulse or voltage amplitudes, respectively, must be conducted via the leads, connectors and, if necessary, through the BMS, which would falsify the measurements, since all parts between the battery and the measuring point are also measured. Finally, the measured impedance rise is a good indication for the decreasing SoH, but there is no direct correlation between both values which can be seen in Figure 1. Figure 1 shows the measurement results for a total of 1438 identical NMC cells with a nominal capacity of 1,95 Ah. 484 cells are new while the remaining 954 cells were used in two identical BEV's. Over a period of 3 years the batteries were used. It should be noted that BEV 2 has a slightly higher mileage than BEV 1, the average charge throughput per cell and the average module temperature of BEV 2 were slightly higher than for BEV 1. Figure 1a) illustrates the real part of the impedance at zero crossing in a Nyquist-Plot and the corresponding capacities of the cells under investigation. Figure 1b) shows the real part that corresponds to the diameter of the semi-circle of a Nyquist-Plot with the corresponding capacity values. Both diagrams show that the impedance of the different cells of the respective BEV's show a possible direct correlation with the capacity but with very large deviations in all three investigated groups. This makes it difficult to make a sound statement about the SoH of the cells. At the same time, the impedance shows correlations with other parameters such as temperature, stress collective and the respective SoC [4]. For these reasons in particular, it appears that the EIS and Internal Resistance Measurement are not suitable for implementation in an external test device.

The sum of the results show that Coulomb Counting is at the moment the most suitable testing method for an external testing device. GPR and DVC could be possible methods to decrease testing time while achieving a high accuracy. Adaptive Methods combine a high possible accuracy and a short testing time, but the accessibility of battery data through the BMS is questionable at the moment. With future norms and rules that are targeting the accessibility of battery data by providing a standardized communication this drawback could be targeted. Currently, the most important disadvantages of Adaptive Methods are the limitation to a few cell chemistries at the same time and the high effort in advance. This limits the test device and for the implementation of a new cell chemistry, for example in a possible on-line database, a large number of test data sets is required. The use of EIS and the Internal Resistance Measurement, does not seem practical, because too many other components of the battery and environmental conditions could falsify the measurement results. Furthermore, the direct correlation between the measurable resistances and the SoH of the battery is not given. Also, the test duration of EIS is too long for the application in an automotive service environment.

Figure 5: Evaluation Results

5 Conclusion

This study gives an overview of the actually discussed and used SoH determination methods and tries to evaluate the most suitable method for an external testing device for an automotive service application. A multitude of different methods is carried out and presented due to deep literature research and expert interviews. Thereby, the response of the expert interviews was very low. This shows how critical the topic of SoH determination is for companies in the automotive business. Through the literature review and the subsequent evaluation process the most suitable method for an external testing device is identified. Coulomb counting currently offers the best combination of characteristics to meet the defined parameters. The parameters used have been chosen to reflect the requirements and conditions that occur in an automotive service environment. Gaussian Process Regression and Differential Voltage Curves could be possible alternatives for the searched application. The main reason is the possible reduction of the test duration compared to the Coulomb Counting, because no complete charge / discharge cycles have to be run. But before these methods can be used, a sufficiently large database must be built up in advance. The Adaptive Methods are not yet practical enough for use in an external battery tester, which is mainly due to the high effort in advance and the limitation to one or a few cell chemistries at the same time. Furthermore, the availability of the required data via the BMS is questionable. But with an adaptation of standards and laws in the future, these methods show promising approaches for the application in such an external testing device. Battery resistance measurements, like Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy, are considered to be not suitable due to the lack of a direct correlation of capacity and resistance. The further procedure is followed by a practical validation of the Coulomb Counting, Differential Voltage Curves and Gaussian Process Regression on cell and module level.

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